

Influence of Ionic Strength On Reaction Rates

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The influence of ionic strength on the rate of reactions has been given in the form of an equation employing Kirkwood's expression for the activity coefficient of an ion with an asymmetric ion atmosphere. It shows a parabolic dependence of $\log k_\mu$ on $\sqrt{\mu}$.

The rate constant for a reaction

taking place in a solution of ionic strength μ was formulated by Bronsted¹ and Bjerrum² by the relation

$$k_\mu = k_0 \frac{f_{R_1} \cdot f_{R_2}}{f_X} \quad (1)$$

where f terms refer to the activity coefficients of the reacting species and of the critical complex X , and k_0 the rate constant in a medium of zero ionic strength. The same relation also follows readily from the transition state theory³. The reference state for the measurement of activity coefficients may, for reactions in solutions, be taken to be the infinitely dilute solution of dielectric constant D . If it be assumed that the dielectric constant is not affected by changes in the ionic strength of the medium, the activity coefficient factors in (1) can be substituted by the Debye Huckel expression. The familiar Bronsted equation then takes the form

$$\ln k_\mu = \ln k_0 + \frac{2Z_{R_1} Z_{R_2} A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \beta a \sqrt{\mu}} \quad (2)$$

When μ is sufficiently small so as to make $\beta a \sqrt{\mu}$ small compared to unity, one obtains either

$$\ln k_\mu = \ln k_0 + 2Z_{R_1} Z_{R_2} A \sqrt{\mu} \quad (3)$$

or

$$\ln k_\mu = \ln k_0 + 2Z_{R_1} Z_{R_2} A \sqrt{\mu} - 2Z_{R_1} Z_{R_2} A \beta a \mu \quad (4)$$

which is obtained by a binomial expansion and retention of terms upto the first power of μ . Relation (3) has been found to be generally valid⁴ in a wide variety of experiments involving ion-ion and ion-dipole reactions while relation (4) has scarcely been used.

1. J. N. Bronsted, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1922, **102**, 169.
2. N. Bjerrum, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, **108**, 82.
3. Eyring, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1935, **3**, 492; Polanyi, Evans, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, **31**, 875.
4. La Mer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 3341; La Mer and Kamner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 2832.

It should be pointed out, however, that the use of limiting law expressions are basically dependent on the symmetrical ion atmosphere around the ions concerned. In case the reacting species and the activated complex have specific discrete charges distributed within them, and this is often true for activated complex, the symmetry of the ion atmosphere will not be ensured.

The activity coefficient of a species with an arbitrary charge distribution has been worked out by Kirkwood⁵ which is

$$-\ln f = \left(\frac{\theta_0}{2DkT} \right) \frac{\kappa}{1+\kappa a} + \frac{\kappa^2}{2DkT} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2n+1) \theta_n}{(2n-1)(n+1)^2 a^{2n-1}} \times \left\{ \frac{K_{n-1}(\kappa a)}{K_{n+1}(\kappa a) + \frac{K_{n-1}(\kappa a) n b^{2n+1} \kappa^2}{(n+1)(2n-1)(2n+1) a^{2n-1}}} \right\} \quad (5)$$

Here

$$\theta_n = \sum_j \sum_l e_j e_l r_j^n r_l^n P_n(\cos \theta_{jl}),$$

where P_n 's are the Legendre's polynomials, e_j, e_l etc. the arbitrary charges r_j, r_l the radius vectors of the discrete charge locations, θ_{jl} the angle between the r_j and r_l vectors. K is some polynomial in κa viz.,

$$K_n(\kappa a) = \sum_{s=0}^n \frac{2^s n! (2n-s)!}{s! (2n)! (n-s)!} (\kappa a)^s.$$

where a is the average distance of closest approach and κ is the well known term viz., $[4\pi\epsilon^2 \sum n_i Z_i^2 / DkT]^{\frac{1}{2}}$. The term b occurring in (5) is the radius of the ion considered as a spherical cavity. The polynomials K_n obey the recurrence relation for $n > 1$

$$K_{n+1} - K_n = \frac{\kappa^2 a^2 K_{n-1}}{(2n+1)(2n-1)} \quad (6)$$

The expression for activity coefficient given by (5) is somewhat simplified in that the dielectric constant D_i of the species is neglected in comparison with that of the solvent medium. The relation for the specific reaction rate at any ionic strength can, therefore, be written as

$$\ln k_\mu = \ln k_0 + \ln \left(\frac{f_{R_1}(k) \cdot f_{R_2}(k)}{f_x(k)} \right) \quad (7)$$

The symbol k occurring in the subscripts of the activity coefficient terms refers to Kirkwood's expression for activity coefficients represented by (5). The use of this relation seems prohibitive because of unwieldy nature of $\ln f$. But certain reasonable assumptions concerning the reacting species, the values of κa etc., make its use possible yielding equations connecting k_μ and μ in ion-ion, ion dipole reactions.

5. Kirkwood, *J. Chem. Phys.* 1934, 2, 358.

The essential steps are :

(i) The species which are undergoing reactions, if ionic in character, may be deemed as unipolar; in that case all θ_n terms with $n = 1$ to α vanish, leaving only θ_0 terms.

(ii) If the nature of the reacting species so prevents its description, the reasonable structures with discrete charge distributions should be assumed for the species.

(iii) The structure of the activated complex, suggested on the basis of kinetics and mechanistic study, is essential for theoretical evaluation of $\log(k_\mu/k_0)$ given by (7).

It is often seen that the activated complex, which is suggested, has discrete charges distributed at different points. For such structures, dipole, quadrupole and other higher pole terms arise due to θ_n involved in the expression for $\ln f$.

(iv) To circumvent the difficulty which arises in (ii) and (iii) due to θ_n terms under the Σ sign of (5), it is assumed that the discrete charges are embedded fairly within rather than towards the periphery of the spherical model. Under this condition the infinite sum rapidly converges (Kirkwood—*loc. cit.*, Laidler and Landskroner⁶⁷) making it unnecessary to consider terms with $n > 1$ in computing the value of θ_n .

The apparently formidable difficulty presented by the factor within the parenthesis { } in (5) may be resolved in the following way. While the first factor under the summation sign becomes rapidly small for $n > 1$ because of the rapid convergence of θ_n , the second factor involving the K_n polynomials needs to be examined for n values equal to and greater than 1. Recalling the significances of "a" and "b", it will be reasonable in the utilisation of this expression for kinetic studies to identify "a" with the size of the activated complex and to assume a magnitude for the ratio of "b" to "a", to be $\frac{1}{2}$ (on the higher side) for rough computation. On this basis, for $n = 1$, the factor involving the K_n polynomials in (5) reduces to

$$\frac{K_0}{K_2 + K_0 b^2 \kappa^2 / 12} \quad (5a)$$

Considering the order of magnitude of b^2 and the experimentally employed values of μ in kinetic studies, the second factor turns out to be negligibly small in the usual temperature ranges and for ordinary values of dielectric constant. The expression (5a) thus practically reduces to $\frac{K_0}{K_2}$ i.e., $1/K_2$. Since K_0 is unity.

For values of $n \geq 2$, it can be readily shown, with the help of recurrence relation (6), that the factor involving the K_n polynomials in (5) practically equals K_n/K_{n+2} . Since the latter is always less than unity, and θ_n , as previously argued, becomes rapidly small for $n \geq 2$, the activity coefficient expression in (5) reduces to

$$-\ln f = \left(\frac{\theta_0}{2DkT} \right) \frac{\kappa}{1 + \kappa a} + \frac{3\kappa^2 \theta_1}{8DkT a K_2} \quad (8)$$

6. Laidler and Landskroner, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, **52**, 200.

7. S. V. Anantakrishnan and P. S. Radhakrishnamurti, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, **3**, 336.

The insertion of this activity coefficient expression in (7) leads to

$$\ln k_{\mu} = \ln k_0 + \frac{\kappa}{2DkT(1+\kappa a)} \{ \theta_{0(x)} - \theta_{0(R_1)} - \theta_{0(R_2)} \} + \frac{3}{8} \frac{\kappa^2}{DkT a \bar{K}_2} \{ \theta_{1(x)} - \theta_{1(R_1)} - \theta_{1(R_2)} \} \quad (9)$$

expressing the influence of ionic strength on the rate constant for reactions in solutions.

For ion-ion reaction, where both are unipolar but the activated complex is not, $\theta_{0(R_1)} = Z_{R_1}^2 \epsilon^2$, $\theta_{1(R_1)} = 0$ and similar are the values of the reactant R_2 with Z terms representing the valency. Relation (9) in this case reduces to

$$\ln k_{\mu} = \ln k_0 + \frac{1}{2DkT} \frac{\kappa}{(1+\kappa a)} [(Z_{R_1} + Z_{R_2})^2 \epsilon^2 - Z_{R_1}^2 \epsilon^2 - Z_{R_2}^2 \epsilon^2] + \frac{3}{8} \frac{\kappa^2}{DkT a \bar{K}_2} \theta_{1(x)} \quad (10)$$

Expansion of $\frac{1}{1+\kappa a}$ and neglect of terms beyond the first power of κa yields from above

$$\ln k_{\mu} = \ln k_0 + \frac{Z_{R_1} Z_{R_2} \epsilon^2}{DkT} \kappa + \frac{\kappa^2}{DkT} \left\{ \frac{3}{8 a \bar{K}_2} \theta_{1(x)} - Z_{R_1} Z_{R_2} \epsilon^2 a \right\} \quad (11)$$

For ion dipole reaction ($R_2 = \text{dipole}$), the general equation (9) leads to

$$\ln k_{\mu} = \ln k_0 + \frac{3}{8} \frac{\kappa^2}{DkT a \bar{K}_2} \{ \theta_{1(x)} - \theta_{1(R_2)} \} \quad (12)$$

The values of $\theta_{1(x)}$ in (11) and of $\theta_{1(x)}$, $\theta_{1(R_2)}$ in (12) are to be evaluated from the respective charge distributions in the corresponding activated complexes and in the dipolar molecule R_2 . Evaluations of this kind have been made by Laidler and Landskroner (*loc. cit.*) in considering the effect of dielectric constant on reaction rate constant.

The substitution of K_2 in (11) and (12), may, for actual kinetic studies, be made by an average value \bar{K}_2 taken over the range of ionic strengths used in experiments. This \bar{K}_2 value will depend, apart from ionic strength, on the "a" value of the activated complex.

Equations (11) and (12) on introducing the expression for κ and replacing K_2 by \bar{K}_2 , yield respectively

$$\ln k_{\mu} = \ln k_0 + \frac{8.3 \times 10^6}{(DT)^{3/2}} Z_{R_1} Z_{R_2} \sqrt{\mu} + \frac{1.8 \times 10^{35}}{D^2 T^2} \left[\frac{.37}{a \bar{K}_2} \theta_{1(x)} - 23 \times 10^{-20} Z_{R_1} Z_{R_2} a \right] \mu \quad (11a)$$

which is valid for ion-ion reaction and

$$\ln k_{\mu} = \ln k_0 + \frac{6.7 \times 10^{34}}{D^2 T^2 a \bar{K}_2} [\theta_{1(x)} - \theta_{1(R_2)}] \quad (12a)$$

valid for ion-dipole reaction.

For aqueous solutions with $D = 78$ at 25° , the above pair of relations become, using decadic logarithm

$$\log k_\mu = \log k_0 + 1.01 Z_{R_1} Z_{R_2} \sqrt{\mu} + 1.44 \times 10^{26} \left\{ \frac{0.37}{a \bar{K}_2} \theta_{1(x)} - 23 \times 10^{-20} Z_{R_1} Z_{R_2} a \right\} \mu \quad (11b)$$

and

$$\log k_\mu = \log k_0 + \frac{5.4 \times 10^{25}}{a \bar{K}_2} \{\theta_{1(x)} - \theta_{1R_2}\} \mu \quad (12b)$$

Plot of $\log k_\mu$ against $\sqrt{\mu}$ for ion-ion reaction should yield according to (11b) a parabola symmetrical about an axis parallel to the $\log k_\mu$ axis. The contribution of the last term in (11b) is generally small; this fact coupled with the general inaccuracies involved in kinetic experiments make plots for $\log k_\mu$ against $\sqrt{\mu}$ look like straight lines in agreement with equation (3) arrived at on simple application of the limiting law. Again for types of reactions covered by relation 12(b) plots of $\log k_\mu$ against μ would be linear—a case which is not covered by (3) or (4), obtained with the use of Debye Huckel's limiting law expressions. It is thus seen that overall conclusions based on Kirkwood's more rigorous approach are similar to the ones based on (4) in so far as the influence of μ on k_μ is concerned in ion-ion reactions only. It should be noted that the explicit expression for the coefficients of μ in (11b) or (12b) affords us a better insight into the nature of things than can be gathered from (4) based essentially on ion-atmosphere symmetry.

The equation (11b), written in the form,

$$Y = A\mu + B\sqrt{\mu} + C$$

suggests that the vertex of the parabola in a plot of $\log k_\mu$ against $\sqrt{\mu}$ is located at the point

$$\left(-\frac{B}{2A}, -\frac{B^2 - 4AC}{4A} \right)$$

and the latus rectum of the parabola is $1/A$.

The kinetic and the mechanistic studies of many reactions throw light on the nature of the activated complexes and these can be profitably utilised in evaluating A necessary for predicting the value of the rate constant at any ionic strength μ .

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